

**THE EFFECT OF CONDITIONS ON THE WATER RETENTION PROPERTIES
OF BEAN VARIETIES GROWN IN THE CONDITIONS OF SAMARKAND REGION****Oltiboyeva Feruza Malikovna¹****O'roqov Sirojiddin Xudayberdiyevich²***1. PhD student of Lalmikor agricultural research institute**2. Teacher of Plant Physiology Department of Samarkand State University named after**Sharof Rashidov**yhamidova@mail.ru***Annotation**

In this article, the ability of leaves of bean varieties to retain water under normal and arid conditions of typical gray soils in the Pastdargom region of the Samarkand region is studied and also the characteristics of drought resistance of these varieties are analyzed. The research is described on the analysis of the physiological and biochemical bases of adaptation in the selection of drought-resistant bean varieties in the Samarkand region, as well as the selection and production of valuable highyielding varieties suitable for this region.

Keywords: Samarkand region, bean varieties, water-holding capacity, leguminous crops, physiological characteristics.

Аннотация

В данной статье изучена способность листьев сортов фасоли удерживать воду в нормальных и засушливых условиях типичных серозёмов Пастдаргомского района Самаркандской области, а также проанализированы характеристики засухоустойчивости сортов. Описаны исследования по анализу физиолого-биохимических основ адаптации при селекции засухоустойчивых сортов фасоли в Самаркандской области, а также подробу и производству ценных высокоурожайных сортов, пригодных для данного региона.

Ключевые слова: Самаркандской области, сорта фасоли, водоудерживающая способность, зернобобовый культуры, физиологические особенности.

Enter. As a result of the decrease of water resources in our republic and the sharp increase in the demand for water in the sectors of the economy, it is now necessary to plant varieties of plants with low demand for water in the cultivation of crops, to make good use of areas freed from grain as repeated crops, and to get a good harvest. is one of the current issues of the day. By 2030, the global water shortage is expected to be 40 percent. Therefore, it is

necessary to select crop varieties of drought-resistant plants for high yield, test agrotechnical measures in practice, and introduce scientifically based plants with high economic efficiency in large areas [1].

In the XXI century, water is taking the leading place among the problems that concern mankind. Because it is becoming more difficult to provide water to irrigated areas, the areas for repeated crops are shrinking, and previously irrigated areas are turning into dry areas. Above we listed only a few problems that arise with irrigation water. It can be seen that these problems of effective use of irrigation water and provision of high-quality agricultural products to the population are urgent [3]. Providing the population with high-quality agricultural products, especially taking into account the importance of beans among the products that satisfy the needs of the population for protein, we aim to cultivate beans select drought-resistant varieties, and introduce them into production in our research.

Research methodology. Field experiments were planted in the Pastdargom district of the Samarkand region. Field experiment under two different conditions CHDNS (Limited Field Moisture Capacity) 70% and CHDNS 50%. The first variety of beans, " Oddiy loviya ", the second variety "Ravot", the third variety " Maxsuldor " and the fourth variety "Qorako'z" were selected.

When preparing the land for planting, the area to be planted was cleared of previous plant residues, and the field was irrigated. When the field was matured, it was plowed to a depth of 25-30 cm, the ground was prepared for planting and seeds were sown. In our research field, bean seeds were sown in the first decade of July.

Materials and methods. Scientific research work was carried out in the typical gray soil conditions of the Pastdargom district of the Samarkand region. The climate of the region is continental, with strong solar radiation, diurnal and seasonal changes, long hot and dry summer seasons, and slightly cold winters. However, winter is warmer because it is surrounded by mountains from the north, northeast, and east. The average temperature in January is 1.9°C, July is 27.2°C, minimum temperature is 26°C, maximum temperature is 44°C. Annual precipitation is 328 mm, mainly in winter and spring. Today, the temperature in such regions is relatively high, as a result of which drought threatens the growth and development of plants, the cultivation of plants resistant to drought and heat in such regions is of great economic importance. [5].

Research was carried out in the form of laboratory and field experiments. During the research, the characteristics of water storage in the leaves of bean varieties with sufficient moisture and in dry conditions were studied in the development phases. The initial weight of the leaf samples taken for determination was measured on an analytical scale and kept at field

temperature for 2 hours. After 2 hours, the withered leaf was found to be stolen again. The withered leaf was dried for 3 hours at 105°C (according to the method of L.G. Tretyakov, A.S. Sulaymanov) by drying the amount of dry matter in a drying cabinet to a constant mass, and its value was determined. The water-holding capacity of bean varieties is determined by the following equation.

$$x = \frac{b \cdot 100}{A}$$

Here:

X is the ability of leaves to retain water, in %

A is the amount of water in the original leaf, in g

b - the amount of water lost by the leaves during 2 hours of wilting.

Analysis and results. During the growth period, the ability to store water in the laboratory conditions was studied in each option and returned in the section of the phases of the bean crop.

Plants play an important role in the study of the nature of water exchange, in the proper organization of irrigation and other agrotechnological measures, taking into account the environmental conditions. One of the important indicators of the water exchange process of plants is the ability of tissues to store water, and this process, depending on many factors, greatly affects the physiological processes and productivity of the plant. In the conditions of the same soil moisture, some varieties have a strong ability to retain water. This shows that these varieties have low drought tolerance.

In our research, we studied the effect of conditions on the water retention characteristics of bean varieties grown as a repeated crop in fields free from grain and presented the results in Tables 1 and 2.

Leaf water retention capacity of bean cultivars under conditions of sufficient moisture (% of full saturation)

Table 1

№	Varieties	Phases of development	Determination periods						Daily average (% water)	Daily average (% water)	Daily change range
			6 ⁰⁰	8 ⁰⁰	10 ⁰⁰	12 ⁰⁰	14 ⁰⁰	16 ⁰⁰			

										loss)	retention	
1	Common beans	Germination	12,1	14,5	15,6	16,2	17,3	15,3	11,9	14,7	85,3	5,4
2	Ravot		12,8	15,1	15,9	16,7	18,1	16,8	12,4	15,4	84,6	5,7
3	Productive		10,3	11,2	12,8	14,6	15,3	13,1	11,1	12,3	87,7	4,2
4	Black eye		13,4	16,3	16,9	17,8	19,2	17,3	13,2	16,4	83,2	6,6
1	Common beans	Trifoliolate	13,3	14,9	16,3	17,5	19,1	16,8	12,3	15,7	84,3	6,8
2	Ravot		14,1	14,8	16,8	18,1	19,9	17,6	13,0	16,4	83,6	6,9
3	Productive		11,4	12,2	14,1	15,4	16,4	14,8	11,3	13,6	86,4	5,1
4	Black eye		15,8	17,4	20,4	22,2	25,3	20,8	16,4	16,5	82,5	8,9
1	Common beans	Shonalash	14,6	15,6	18,2	19,8	21,4	17,4	13,2	17,2	82,8	8,9
2	Ravot		14,8	15,9	18,4	20,1	22,5	18,8	14,3	17,8	82,2	8,2
3	Productive		11,9	13,8	14,9	16,1	18,2	16,3	12,1	15,0	86,0	6,1
4	Black eye		15,4	18,6	20,3	21,7	24,8	20,5	14,4	19,4	80,6	10,4
1	Common beans	Flowering	16,3	17,9	19,1	20,7	23,4	19,2	13,8	18,4	81,4	9,6
2	Ravot		15,8	18,1	19,3	21,3	24,2	20,7	14,3	19,1	80,9	9,9
3	Productive		13,5	15,3	16,1	18,8	20,4	17,8	13,6	16,6	83,4	6,8
4	Black eye		16,6	19,9	21,1	22,2	26,6	23,4	15,4	20,8	79,2	11,8

			8	4	8	5	7					
1	Common beans	Beaning	13,3	14,7	16,3	18,6	22,2	17,8	13,1		83,4	8,8
2	Ravot		14,4	17,8	18,3	19,5	23,3	18,8	14,9		82,0	8,4
3	Productive		10,1	13,8	14,7	16,5	18,8	16,3	10,8		85,0	7,5
4	Black eye		16,3	18,7	20,4	21,6	24,7	22,3	14,6		80,3	10,1
										16,6		
										18,0		
										15,0		
										19,7		

Leaf water storage capacity of bean cultivars under arid conditions

Table 2

№	Varieties	Phases of development	Determination periods							Daily average (% water loss)	Daily average (% water retention)	Daily change range
			6 ⁰⁰	8 ⁰⁰	10 ⁰⁰	12 ⁰⁰	14 ⁰⁰	16 ⁰⁰	18 ⁰⁰			
1	Common beans	Germination	9,8	11,3	13,2	14,7	16,5	14,1	11,3	12,9	87,1	5,2
2	Ravot		10,1	12,5	13,8	14,5	17,6	13,8	12,3	13,5	86,5	5,3
3	Productive		8,1	9,2	10,4	12,1	15,3	13,1	11,5	11,4	88,6	3,8
4	Black eye		11,4	13,8	14,6	15,9	18,7	16,4	12,6	14,8	85,2	6,1
1	Common beans	Trifoliolate	11,8	12,8	13,9	15,6	17,8	14,1	11,5	13,9	86,5	6,3
2	Ravot		11,4	13,6	14,8	15,7	18,1	15,2	10,6	11,9	85,2	6,2
3	Productive		9,3	10,4	12,6	13,2	16,3	13,5	11,7	12,3	87,7	4,6

4	Black eye		12, 3	14, 6	16, 3	17, 8	21, 8	17, 1	12, 7	16,1	83,9	7,5
1	Common beans	Shonalash	11, 1	13, 6	14, 7	17, 1	19, 6	15, 5	11,5	14,7	85,3	8,1
2	Ravot		12, 6	14, 8	15, 6	17, 8	21, 5	17, 3	13, 6	16,1	83,9	7,9
3	Productive		10, 7	11, 6	12, 3	13, 8	17, 8	15, 6	12, 1	13,3	86,7	5,7
4	Black eye		14, 6	16, 7	19, 6	23, 8	24, 8	22, 5	15, 2	19,5	80,5	9,6
1	Common beans	Flowering	12, 4	14, 7	16, 8	19, 3	22, 7	17, 4	13, 4	16,7	83,3	9,3
2	Ravot		13, 6	16,7	17, 3	19, 5	23, 8	19, 6	14, 2	17,8	82,2	9,6
3	Productive		11, 1	12, 6	13, 8	15, 3	19, 4	16, 3	13, 1	14,5	85,5	6,1
4	Black eye		15, 3	18, 3	20, 6	24, 3	25, 4	22, 6	14, 7	19,7	80,3	10,7
1	Common beans	Beaning	11, 4	13, 2	15, 6	18, 8	19, 6	16, 4	12, 9	15,2	84,8	9,7
2	Ravot		12, 2	14, 5	15, 3	17, 6	22, 2	17, 6	14, 9	16,1	83,9	7,3
3	Productive		10, 4	11, 3	12, 4	14, 6	17, 2	15, 3	10, 7	13,1	86,9	6,5
4	Black eye		14, 7	16, 2	18, 4	23, 1	23, 6	21, 8	14, 1	19,7	80,3	9,5

As a result of our research, it was observed that the water retention property of leaves decreases from morning to 2 pm, and then the water retention property increases again until evening. This pattern was observed in all varieties and phases under conditions of arid and sufficient moisture. It was determined that the time of the lowest water level was at 14:00.

During the germination phase, high water retention was observed in the "Maxsuldor" variety under conditions of sufficient moisture, the average daily water retention amount in the "Maxsuldor" variety was 87.7%, and the range of daily variation was 4.2. A relatively low indicator of water retention was observed in the "Qorako'z" variety. The amount of water

retention in this variety was 83.2%, and the range of daily variation was 6.6. A relatively high water retention capacity was observed in the "Maxsuldor" variety even in the germination phase in arid conditions. The average daily water storage capacity was found to be 88.6%, and the range of daily variation was 3.8. The " Qorako'z " variety had a lower result than the other varieties, the amount of water retention was 85.2%, and the range of daily variation was 6.1.

It was observed that the amount of water in the leaves of bean cultivars during the three-leaflet and tillering phase decreased slightly compared to the germination phase, and the high water retention property can be seen in the "Maxsuldor" variety in these phases, that is, it was 88.8% in the three-leaflet phase in the morning, and at 2:00 p.m. was found to be at least 81.9%. In this phase, it was noted that the daily average was 86.4%, and the daily variation range was equal to 5.1. A relatively low indicator of water retention was found in the " Qorako'z " variety in these phases as well, the daily average water retention was 82.5%, the range of daily variation was 8.9, and the rest of the varieties were intermediate. In arid conditions, it was observed that the water retention capacity of the " Maxsuldor " variety is higher than that of the other varieties even in these phases. The average daily water storage capacity was found to be 86.7%, and the range of daily variation was 5.7. A lower result was found in the " Qorako'z " variety, in which the average daily water retention capacity was 82.5%, and the range of daily variation was 8.9.

It was found that the amount of water in the leaves of bean varieties in the podding phase is slightly reduced compared to the flowering phase. A general rule was also observed in this phase, i.e., the amount of water in the leaves was high at 6 a.m., the amount of water in the leaves decreased as the air temperature increased, and the lowest amount of water was observed at 2 p.m. the highest can be seen in the " Maxsuldor " variety, that is, the daily average was 85.0% and the daily variation range was 7.5. It was found that the daily average of the water retention property was 80.3%, the range of daily variation was 10.1%, and the rest of the varieties took an intermediate place. Even in dry conditions, the quality of water retention in the cross-section of varieties was determined in the " Maxsuldor " variety, while the lower indicator was found in the "Qorako'z" variety.

It is also important to choose and use varieties that are resistant to drought. Such varieties have a high synthetic ability of enzymes, a high amount of bound water, a relatively high concentration of cell sap, a strong ability to store water, and a lack of ability to accumulate organic matter. These indicators describe the physiological and biochemical nature of drought tolerance.

Summary. In the results of our research, it was found that the property of water retention in the leaves in the conditions of the environment with sufficient humidity and in the conditions

of the arid environment is higher in the variety " Maxsuldor " compared to other varieties in all phases of development. Taking this into account, in the conditions of the Samarkand region, it is possible to achieve high economic efficiency if the " Maxsuldor " variety is cultivated as a repeated crop in the fields empty of grain.

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